

A Study of the Attitude of the Schedule Tribe Parents Towards Education of their School Going Children

Chinmoy Das¹, Satyajit Kar² and Hitasish Bhowmick³

¹Research Scholar, Swami Vivekananda Centre for Multidisciplinary Research in Educational Studies, RKMSM, Belur Math, Howrah

²Assistant Professor, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira (CTE), Belur Math, Howrah

³Assistant Professor, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira (CTE), Belur Math, Howrah

ABSTRACT : Indian society has been the most classified society. It has been classified on the basis of various castes. One of them is ST the researcher focuses on the attitude of the ST parents towards their children's education. Parent's positive attitude towards their children's education is important in determining school attendance and academic achievement of the said children. The present and future studies of students will be enhanced by the favorable attitude towards schooling. The present study was conducted to enquire the attitude of parents towards education whose children are enrolled in school and whose children are non-enrolled in school. And to compare the attitude of parents towards with respect to gender, enrolment of children at primary stage of schooling. A study administered on 200 samples from rural area of Birbhum district, west Bengal. Major findings wear observed that, male parents and female parents not differ significantly in their attitude towards education of their children. Moreover, parents of enrolled children and parents of non-enrolled children differ significantly in their attitude towards education of their children.

Keywords : Attitude, Schedule tribe, School going children

Introduction

Indian society has been the most classified society. It has been classified on the basis of various castes. The caste is defined as a hereditary occupational group limited to a region

with certain constraints of commensality. The very nature of motionlessness and lack of interaction has made the caste system very strict and nourished inequality permanently. Education is a fundamental human right and necessary for

the necessity of all other human rights. It provides individual freedom and empowerment and many important development benefits. Education is a power by which marginalized people economically and socially can lift themselves up and participate fully as citizens. Yet millions of children and adults are deprived of educational opportunities, many as a result of poverty. Education seeks to unfold the latent qualities of a person, Therefore giving full individual development. The researcher lives in Birbhum district in West Bengal and a large number of schedule tribe live here. As the researcher is an inhabitant of this area so he is well aware of the education condition of the Schedule tribe. In my schedule tribe area schedule tribe children do not get enrolled even after having schools nearby, again many of them are dropped out within few years. There may be so many reasons of these problems such as economic, social, caste, and illiteracy. But the researcher thinks parents' attitude is mostly responsible. Parent's positive attitude towards their children's education is important in determining school attendance and academic achievement of the said children. The present and future studies of students will be enhanced by the Favorable attitude towards schooling.

However, the problem of the present study is to inquire into the Attitude of the Schedule Tribe Parents towards Education of their School going children around suri sub-division.

Attitude

Attitude is a psychological tendency; it is measurable and changeable if it is influenced by emotion or behavior. Attitude is also an emotional feeling about things, persons, conduct and education. Parent's positive attitude helps

their children for better education, whereas negative attitude creates problems for their children's education. The researcher wants to show that parental attitude is the main factor for having their children enrolled or non-enrolled in education.

Schedule tribe

The erstwhile untouchables were listed by the government in different schedules to consider them as different category, in order to further their social, educational, economic and other interests. Such list has been prepared by the respected state governments.

School going children

By school going children the researcher means to say that it is those children who go to school for learning, they are enrolled children, and the children who do not go to school or the dropout children are non-school going children or non-enrolled children.

Review of related literature

Doger.,Azeem.andFeroze (2011), study on Parents' Gender Biased Attitude towards Education. This studies main objective were 1) the attitude of parents towards the education of their girl child. The study will consist of the parents of the girls enrolled in elementary classes living in three communities (Model Town, Township, and Shahdra) of different socio-economic levels. In this research Likert type attitude scale are developed. Seven areas are covered in this scale. Major finding are 1) Parents have highly positive attitude towards the education of their girl child and parents belonging to the higher socio-economic status have more favourable attitude towards the education of their girl child.

Kotwani(2012),in his study attitude of parents towards girl's education. Objectives of the study 1) attitudes of parents towards the girl's education. 2) To compare the attitudes of male & female parents towards girl's education. In the present study descriptive Survey Method has been used, Total 200 parents from urban and rural areas of Akola & Amravati districts of Maharashtra have been chosen randomly, t-test were used for the statistical analysis of the data. And major finding are the parents have high attitude towards girl's education and there is no significant difference in the attitude of Male & Female parents towards girl's education.

Samal, (2012), in his study parents' attitude towards schooling and education of children. Main objectives are **i)** to examine the attitudes of parents towards schooling and education of their children. **ii)** To compare the parents belonging to tribal and non-tribal communities with regard to their attitude towards children's schooling and education. **iii)** To examine whether there exists a significant gender difference in attitudes of parents towards children's education. He using self-made attitude scale, descriptive statistics included calculation on mean standard deviation of the tabulated data and inferential statistics t-test. The study revealed that, overall, the attitude of the respondents was found to be moderately favorable towards schooling and education of their children. The study throws light on the fact that growing awareness regarding literacy and education;

Rabia & Yaari (2012), Parent's attitudes and behavior, the learning environment, and their influence on children's early reading achievement. The objectives of study are **i)** parental attitudes towards reading, behavior, and

the learning environment that families convey to their children directly affect reading achievement. **ii)** Parental attitudes affect reading achievement when they are mediated by behavior, only in environments that support learning. Using the classified random sampling procedure and attitude questionnaire of parents toward reading, interview. Descriptive statistics used t test. The study revealed that parents' supportive attitudes have a significant positive influence on the reading performance of their children.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To study the attitude of parents towards education whose children are enrolled in school.
- 2) To study the attitude of parents towards education whose children are non-enrolled in school.
- 3) To compare the attitude of parents towards with respect to gender, enrolment of children at primary stage of schooling.
- 4) To compare the attitude of parents towards with respect to gender, non-enrolment of children at primary stage of schooling.

Hypotheses

H₀1 There is no significant difference between male parents and female parents in their attitude towards education of their children.

H₀2 There is no significant difference between parents of Enrolled children and parents of Non-Enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between male parents of enrolled children and male parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

H₀₄ There is no significant difference between female parents of enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

H₀₅ There is no significant difference between male parents of enrolled children and female parents of enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

H₀₆ There is no significant difference between male parents of non-enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

H₀₇ There is no significant difference between parents of lower primary children and parents of upper primary children in their attitude towards education of their children.

Delimitation of the study

The present study is delimited to only Bengali medium schools recognized by W.B.B.S.E have been selected in rural area from Suri block in Birbhum district. Researcher has taken 200 (100 enrolled, 100 non enrolled schedule tribe students' parents) schedule tribe parents as research sample.

Methodology of the study

Variables in present study

The types of institution, sex of the student parents (male/female), have been considered as independent variables, and attitude of schedule tribe parents towards education has been considered as dependent variable.

Population

The researcher has selected a schedule tribe area in the subdivision of Suri in Birbhum district of West Bengal as the survey area. The researcher has selected a population of 200 persons.

Sample and sample design

The sample for the study consisted of residents Naguripanchayat of subdivision of Suri in Birbhum district of West Bengal. This village consists of five hamlets, namely-

Taldihi, Jamdhi, Katabuni, Laturbana, Latabuni. The data was collected from the 200 respondents (100 enrolment students' parents and 100 non-enrolment students' parents) from in this village. The total number of the male respondents was 100 and that of female was 100. The respondents were parents who had one or more than one school going children. They belonged to the age range of 25-55 years.

Table 1: Showing the sample design

Stage	Area of school			
	Rural area			
Primary Education	No. of male parents of enrolled children	No. of female parents of enrolled children	No. of male parents of non-enrolled children	No. of female parents of non-enrolled children
	50	50	50	50

Tools used

The data was collected through a questionnaire consisting of 32 statements, all pertaining to schooling and education of children. 18 numbers of statements are positive and 14 number of statement are negative statements were included in the questionnaire. The respondents were asked to rate each of the statements on a five-point scale (where 1 denotes strongly agree, 2 denotes agree, 3 denotes no comment, 4 denotes disagree and 5 denotes strongly disagree).

included from each of the household. Assessment was done individually in Bengali and Santali language. Santali language helps me my interpreter. After the respondents completed the rating of statements, data was also collected about the future plans for their child education and other miscellaneous matters through open ended questions.

Presentation of data

Data analysis:

H₀1: There is no significant difference

Table no. 2 Descriptive statistic of all groups

Group	Mean	N	Std.Deviation
Male	107.41	100	2.239
Female	107.36	100	2.262
Parents of enrolled children	125.7900	100	9.79414
Parents of non-enrolled children	88.9800	100	15.24678
Male parents of enrolled children	125.48	50	11.036
Male parents of non-enrolled children	89.34	50	14.977
Female parents of enrolled children	126.10	50	8.474
Female parents of non-enrolled children	88.62	50	15.6555
Parents of lower primaryeducation children	58	126.19	9.12
Parents of upper primaryeducation children	42	125.24	10.74

Procedure of the data collection

Before collecting the data field visits were done. At the initial stage of field work each houses were numbered. Respondents were

between male parents and female parents in their attitude towards education of their children.

The table 3 shows the t-test was applied to

Table -3

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at
Male	100	107.41	22.386	2.239	198	0.987	0.05 0.01
Female	100	107.36	22.618	2.262			1.97 2.6

compare the parent's attitude towards education of their children. At the df 198 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.97 and 1.60 respectively.

The calculated t value (0.987) is less than both critical t value that $0.987 < 1.98$ at 0.05 level and $0.987 < 2.61$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the obtained result therefore null hypothesis is accepted here. Then it can be said that, there is no significant difference between male parents and female parents in their attitude towards education.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between parents of enrolled children and parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

The calculated t value (2.61) is more than both critical t value that $2.61 > 1.97$ at 0.05 level and $2.61 > 2.60$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the obtained result therefore null hypothesis is rejected. Then it can be said that, there is significant difference between parents of enrolled children and parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education

H₀3 There is no significant difference between male parents of enrolled children and male parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

The table 5 shows the t-test wear applied to compare the total male parents of enrolled children and total male parents of non-enrolled

Table - 4

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at	
Parents of Enrolled children	100	125.79	9.79414	0.97941	198	2.61	0.05	0.01
Parents of non-Enrolled children	100	88.98	15.2468	1.52468			1.97	2.6

The table 4 shows the t-test wear applied to compare the total parents of enrolled children and total parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education. At the df 198 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.97 and 1.60 respectively.

children in their attitude towards education. At the df 98 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.98 and 1.63 respectively.

The calculated t value (1.41) is less than both critical t value that $1.41 < 1.98$ at 0.05 level

Table - 5

Type of Parents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at	
Male Parents of Enrolled children	50	125.48	11.036	1.56	98	1.41	0.05	0.01
Male Parents of non-Enrolled children	50	89.34	14.977	2.118			1.98	2.63

and $1.41 < 2.63$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the obtained result therefore null hypothesis is accepted. Then it can be said that, there is no significance difference between male parents of enrolled children and male parents of non-Enrolled children in their attitude towards education.

H₀4 There is no significant difference between female parents of enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

obtained result null hypothesis is rejected. Then it can be said that, There is significance difference between female parents of enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education.

H₀5 There is no significant difference between male parents of enrolled children and female parents of enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

The table 7 shows the t-test wear applied to compare the total male parents of enrolled

Table - 6

Type of Parents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std.Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at	
Female Parents of Enrolled children	52	126.1	8.474	1.198	98	6.68	0.05	0.01
Female Parents of non-Enrolled children	50	88.62	15.655	2.214			1.98	2.63

The table 6 shows the t-test wear applied to compare the total female parents of enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education. At the df 98 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.98 and 1.63 respectively.

The calculated t value (6.68) is more than both critical t value that $6.68 < 1.98$ at 0.05 level and $6.68 < 2.63$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the

children and female parents of Enrolled children in their attitude towards education . At the df 98 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.98 and 2.63 respectively that the calculated t value (0.75) is less than both critical t value that $0.75 < 1.98$ at 0.05 level and $0.75 < 2.63$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the obtained result therefore null hypothesis is accepted. Then it can be said that, There is no significance difference between male parents

Table -7

Type of Parents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std.Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at	
Male Parents of Enrolled children	50	125.48	11.036	1.56	98	0.75	0.05	0.01
Female Parents of Enrolled children	50	126.1	8.473	1.198			1.98	2.63

of enrolled children and female parents of enrolled children in their attitude towards education.

H₀6 There is no significant difference between male parents of non-enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education of their children.

significant difference between male parents of non-enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education.

H₀7 There is no significant difference between parents of lower primary children and parents of upper primary children in their attitude towards education of their children.

Table - 8

Type of Parents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at	
Male Parents of non-Enrolled children	50	89.34	14.977	2.11807	98	0.81	0.05	0.01
Female Parents of non-Enrolled children	50	88.62	15.6556	2.21404			1.98	2.63

The table 8 shows the t-test was applied to compare the total male parents of non-enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children in their attitude towards education. At the df 98 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.98 and 2.63 respectively.

That the calculated t value (0.81) is less than both critical t value that $0.81 < 1.98$ at 0.05 level and $0.81 < 2.63$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the obtained result therefore null hypothesis is accepted. Then it can be said that there is no

The table 9 shows the t-test was applied to compare the total parents of lower primary education children and parents of upper primary education children in their attitude towards education. At the df 98 the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 0.01 level of significance are 1.98 and 2.63 respectively.

That the calculated t value (0.63) is less than both critical t value that $0.63 < 1.98$ at 0.05 level and $0.63 < 2.63$ at 0.01 level. Therefore the obtained result therefore null hypothesis is accepted. Then it can be said that there is no

Table - 9

Type of Parents	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	't' ratio	Critical value of 't' at	
Parents of lower primary education children	58	126.189	9.122	1.198	98	0.63	0.05	0.01
Parents of upper primary education children	42	125.238	10.743	1.658			1.98	2.63

significant difference between parents of lower primary education children and parents of upper primary education children in their attitude towards education.

Major findings of the study

After analyzing the data the researcher has found the following facts:

- 1) Male parents and female parents not differ significantly in their attitude towards education of their children.
- 2) Parents of enrolled children and parents of non-enrolled children differ significantly in their attitude towards education of their children.
- 3) Male parents of enrolled children and male parents of non-enrolled children differ significantly in their attitude towards education of their children.
- 4) Female parents of enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children differ significantly in their attitude towards education of their children.
- 5) Male parents of enrolled children and female parents of enrolled children not differ significantly in their attitude towards education.
- 6) Male parents of non-enrolled children and female parents of non-enrolled children not differ significantly in their attitude towards education.

Conclusion

Since independence no doubt a change has been found in the literacy level as well as the perception regarding schooling and education but still there are some hindrances in getting such

facilities for schedule tribes which affects parent's attitude towards education of their children.

The researcher has worked upon 200 samples under Suri sub-division in Birbhum district. The researcher has analyzed the data and found there is no difference between male and female parents attitude towards their children's education. Enrolment and non-enrolment of the children do not depend only on the attitude of their parents. So the researcher thinks that there should be other reasons.

To compare the attitude of the enrolment and non-enrolment parents. The 't' test was employed to find out whether the enrolment parents differed significantly from non-enrolment parents in their attitude towards education of their children. The results indicated that there was no significant difference between the enrolment and non-enrolment parents attitude towards education of their children. Though both groups getting and consuming all the same facilities but the main reason to make their children enrolled or non-enrolled in school is parental attitude.

To compare the attitude of the lower primary parents and upper primary parents, mean scores of these two groups were found out separately. The t test was employed to find out whether there is not differ between enrolled and non-enrolled male parent's attitude. The researcher has come to the conclusion that attitude of enrolled parents are positive than attitude of non-enrolled children parents.

References

- Mangal, S.K. (2002). *Statistic in psychology in education*. New Delhi: A.P.H. Publishing Corporation.

- Government of West Bengal, 2004, West Bengal Human Development Report, Development and Planning Department, May.
- Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan-Tribal Development plan (2007), Ministry of Human Resources Development Government of India. New Delhi.
- District Statistical Handbook Birbhum(2008), Bureau of Applied Economics & Statistics-Government of west Bengal.
- Bagai, S., Nundy, N. (2009). Tribal Education-a fine balance. New Delhi:Rakesh Press.
- Nayak.K.A.,Rao.K.V.,(2009). New Delhi:A.P.H. publishing corporation. Pp.21-23.
- Rao.B.D.,(2010). Education For All-the global consensus, New Delhi:A.P.H. publishing corporation.
- Srinivas.N.,(2010).Tribal Education, New Delhi; A.P.H. publishing corporation. Pp.1-3.
- Dogar,A., Azeem, M. & Feroze, S. (2011) "parent's gender biased attitude towards education", international journal of humanities and social science;vol-1.no.16; November
- Kotwani,S.,(2012) "Attitude of Parents towards Girl's Education" International Indexed & Referred Research Journal,ISSN-0975-3486,Vol.III.April.
- Rabia, S.A., Yarrri.I., (2012). 'Parent's Attitudes and Behavior, the Learning Environment, and Their Influence on Children's Early Reading Achievement' open Journal of Modern Linguistics; 2012. vol.2, no.4,170-179. <http://www.scirp.org/journal/ojmal>.
- Samal,R.(2012). 'Parents' attitude towards schooling and education of children.'Department of humanities and social science, National Institute of Techeques, Rourkela, Odisha.
- Gupta.P. & Buwade.J.,(2013). "Parental attitude towards the Inclusion Education for their Disabled children" vol.2.ISSN No.-2277-7733.December.
- Fifth survey of Research in Education,ed.M.B.BUCH.New Delhi NCERT
<http://w.w.w.educationinindia.net>
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_India
http://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/RPE-2010-11.pdf
<http://unesdoc.unesco.org>

Received : 12th December, 2014

Accepted : 28th July, 2015